

Business English is divided into two sub-fields, Learning and Teaching. Learning includes Learning Process, Business Writing, and Materials setting off from the side of students. English Skills including listening, reading, and speaking are what students practice while learning Business English. Cooperative Learning is the method for better practice. When studying Business English writing, students not only need to practice writing itself but also are required to expand their business vocabulary and understand foreign business languages to conduct bilingual interpretations. Books, ESP journals, and grammatical school instructions are the types of learning materials that students use for reference.

Teaching in Business English comprises Language Study and Vocational Translation with teachers being dominant in this branch. Communication Case is to teach communication courses with the case method. Language without borders internationalizes Business English by placing communication under multilingual contexts. ESP materials provide guiding support for teaching. Vocational Translation covers vocational training, translation teaching and intercultural communicative teaching. Vocational Training focuses on the cultivation of talents for teaching Business English. Translation Teaching intends to improve the candidates' capabilities of Business English translation by integrating pedagogical theories and multimedia technology into teaching methods. Intercultural Communicative Teaching aims to teach Business English with intercultural and communicative purposes.

Figure 2. The identified sub-fields of Business English from text embeddings.

Implication

This study provides guidance for both Business English educators and learners. Business English educators, such as teachers and instructors, can be informed of teaching content and improve their teaching methods by referring to our interpretation. For students or business professionals, who are interested in Business English, our study enables them to be familiar with subjects so they would be

more capable of applying acquired knowledge in workplaces.

Conclusion

This study identifies sub-fields of Business English by clustering academic works with a text embedding method. The identified sub-fields represent the knowledge structure of Business English well and are expected to strengthen Business English education.

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